

Annual meeting NOVA 2018

28 February – 1 March, Rome, Italy

ATTENDANCE LIST

Institute	Name of participant	Participant's signature
CODA	De Waele Valérie	
BfR	Weiser Armin	
RKI	Haller Sebastian	
RKI	Wilking Hendrik	
DTU	Vigre Håkan	
SSI	Ethelberg Steen	
SSI	Trier Møller Frederik	
INIA	de la Torre Ana	
UCM	Álvarez Sánchez Julio	
ANSES	Henaus Viviane	
ANSES	Huneau Adeline	
ANSES	Sala Carole	
ISS	Scavia Gaia	
IZS	Iannetti Luigi	
RIVM	Evers Eric	
RIVM	Friesema Ingrid	
NIPH	Grøneng Gry	
NIPH	Jore Solveig	
NVI	Jonsson Malin	
NVI	Kausrud Kyrre	
PHAS	Mörk Marie	
SVA	Dórea Fernanda	
SVA	Frössling Jenny	
SVA	Rosendal Thomas	
SVA	Widgren Stefan	
SVA	Ågren Estelle	
APHA	Arnold Mark	
PHE	Larkin Lesley	

RIVM

Arno Swart

